

Automatic Hydraulic Bending Machine

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Abstract: The construction industry is increasingly focusing on automation to enhance productivity and reduce labor costs. However, bending rods and pipes for beams and columns still relies heavily on manual labor due to the high cost and complexity of existing machines. This paper presents a cost-effective solution: the Hydraulic Rod Bending Machine. Utilizing hydraulic pressure, this machine efficiently bends aluminum, mild steel, and copper rods without the need for repositioning, significantly improving operational efficiency. The machine comprises a hydraulic cylinder, screw drive loading mechanism, and a fixture to hold the rod in place during the bending process. By continuously bending square-shaped rods, it eliminates the inefficiencies associated with manual and automatic machines. The Hydraulic Rod Bending Machine addresses the quality and quantity demands of the growing steel sector, providing a high-quality, cost-effective alternative. This innovation ensures precise bends and is adaptable to various construction needs, making it a valuable tool for modern construction projects.

Keywords: bending operation, hydraulic system, bar, automatic rod making, fixture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The hydraulic bending press is an incredibly versatile machine, perfect for tasks like shearing, punching, bending, scrolling, and pressing various parts. It's ideal for metal fabricators and iron workers, fitting well into small to medium-sized industries where keeping production costs low is essential. Compared to other pipe bending machines, operating a hydraulic pipe bending machine is straightforward (Colliers Encyclopedia, 1997).

In tube bending, you start by loading a tube into the bender and clamping it between two dies: the clamping block and the forming die. The tube is also supported by two other dies, the wiper die and the pressure die. Mechanical force pushes the tube against a die, shaping it to match the die. Sometimes, the tube is rotated and rolled around the die, or pushed through rollers to create a curve. To prevent the tube from collapsing, a mandrel might be placed inside. The wiper die helps prevent creasing during bending and is usually made from softer materials like aluminum or brass to avoid scratching the tube (Kalpakjian, 1997 and Acherkan, 1973).

Most parts of the tube bender are made from hardened steel to ensure durability, especially the clamping block, rotating form block, and pressure die. However, parts that come into contact with the moving tube, like the pressure die and wiper die, are made from softer materials to protect the tube's surface.

Pipe bending machines can be powered in various ways, including manually, pneumatically, hydraulically, or by electric servomotors. Hydraulic machines are particularly popular due to their ability to transfer large amounts of power through small tubes and hoses, thanks to the use of pressurized hydraulic fluid. This fluid is controlled by valves and distributed through hoses and tubes, making hydraulic machinery highly efficient and powerful (Beer and Johnston, 1992 and Dagwa and Ibhadode, 2005).

Overall, the simplicity and efficiency of hydraulic machinery make it a profitable choice for many applications. The 45-ton hydraulic press brake, for example, is suitable for 90% of horizontal press brake tasks and offers a great return on investment, covering a wide range of profitable jobs.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

DC Motor:

A 12V DC motor with a speed of 30 RPM converts electrical energy into mechanical energy. It operates on the principle that a current-carrying conductor placed in a magnetic field experiences a mechanical force. A DC motor is a type of rotary electrical machine that converts direct current (DC) electrical energy into mechanical energy. It operates using the forces produced by magnetic fields. Most DC motors have a mechanism, either electromechanical or electronic, to periodically change the direction of current flow.

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DC motors were the first widely used electric motors because they could be powered by existing DC power distribution systems. They offer excellent speed control over a wide range, either by adjusting the supply voltage or the current in the field windings.

Small DC motors are commonly found in tools, toys, and appliances. Universal motors, which can run on both AC and DC, are used in portable power tools and household appliances. Larger DC motors are used in electric vehicles, elevators, hoists, and steel rolling mills. With the development of power electronics, many applications have shifted from DC to AC motors.

Hydraulic Jack

We opted for a hydraulic cylinder over a screw-drive loading mechanism. A hydraulic system provides constant load control and can quickly correct minor failures and load redistributions during a test, which is more responsive than a screw drive. Additionally, hydraulic test machines offer greater flexibility for cyclic and vibrational testing compared to screw-driven machines.

Construction for the project

The mechanical structure that forms the backbone of this pipe bending machine is built using readily available mild steel (MS) square pipes and metal plates. The fabrication process involves meticulous cutting of the steel components using a grinder. Next, precise holes are drilled using a drill machine to facilitate assembly. Finally, the various pieces are securely welded together, as illustrated in the figure.

The hydraulic jack, the heart of the bending process, is firmly attached to the main structure. This is achieved by welding it onto a robust 16-inch horizontal metal frame with a width of 2 inches. For added stability, two vertical supports, constructed from MS tubes, are positioned strategically. These supports ensure the entire structure remains upright during operation. To further enhance stability, a metal plate is fastened above these supports. Unlike the welded connections below, this plate is secured using nuts and bolts, allowing for easier disassembly if necessary.

Connecting the Power Source: From Motor to Jack

The handle of the hydraulic jack is cleverly linked to a DC motor through a well-designed mechanism. This ensures efficient power transfer during operation. The DC motor itself draws power from a dedicated battery. An ON/OFF switch is positioned conveniently in the circuit, allowing for complete control over the motor's operation and the subsequent activation of the hydraulic jack.

Working

The operation of a hydraulic jack for pipe bending relies on the efficient transfer of energy through a DC motor and a connecting rod. When the DC motor is switched on, it drives the connecting rod, which acts as a pump, initiating the hydraulic process. This initial movement creates a vacuum within the pump chamber.

This vacuum, in turn, draws hydraulic fluid from the reservoir through a one-way valve. As you continue pumping the handle, the one-way valve closes, preventing the backflow of fluid. This continuous pumping action progressively increases the pressure within the pump chamber. The high-pressure fluid then exerts a powerful force against a larger piston located in the lifting chamber.

The pipe intended for bending is positioned between the piston saddle and a dedicated bending structure. As the pressure intensifies within the lifting chamber, the larger piston drives the pipe upwards. This force applied against the pipe, in conjunction with the resistance provided by the bending structure, initiates the bending process.

By adjusting the position and configuration of the bending structure, we can achieve a variety of bending angles on the pipe. This allows for precise control over the final shape of the bent pipe, catering to various construction or engineering needs.

III. RESULTS

The hydraulic machine delivers clean, smooth bends on the pipe material, replicating the desired shape consistently. This ensures the pipe retains its structural integrity and visual appeal.

The hydraulic cylinder acts like a powerful but controlled hand, applying just the right amount of force to achieve an accurate bend at the precise location on the pipe. This eliminates inconsistencies that can occur with manual bending. By automating the process and utilizing controlled hydraulic pressure, it delivers superior accuracy compared to manual bending, ensuring the pipe meets the exact specifications. This level of precision is difficult to achieve consistently with manual bending, making the hydraulic machine ideal for applications where accuracy is paramount.

Manual pipe bending is a physically demanding task that can lead to RSIs in the wrists, back, and shoulders over time. The hydraulic machine automates the bending process, significantly reducing the physical strain on workers. This translates to a healthier and safer work environment for those involved in pipe bending activities.

IV. CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the research and development of this hydraulic pipe bending machine has yielded a promising solution for various bending needs. Here's a breakdown of its key strengths:

1. By automating the bending process, the machine significantly reduces the physical strain on workers, minimizing the risk of repetitive strain injuries.
2. Eliminating manual bending and ensuring consistent quality translates to faster completion times and less rework. This allows workers to focus on other tasks or handle larger workloads.
3. The machine delivers clean, wrinkle-free bends with unmatched accuracy, crucial for applications where aesthetics and structural integrity are paramount.
4. Compared to existing machines, this design aims to be a more affordable option, particularly beneficial for small-scale operations and budget-conscious industries.
5. The modular design allows for modifications like changing the table to accommodate pressing operations using dies and punches, increasing the machine's versatility.

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